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Response of Wild and Edible *Musa* spp. Seedlings to Limiting Moisture Stress

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Banana, one of the world's leading crops is predicted to be highly vulnerable to drought conditions brought about by climate change. Identification of drought tolerant cultivars is one of the long term strategies of addressing the effect of climate change. The National Plant Genetic Resources Laboratory and the Bureau of Plant Industry of the Philippine Department of Agriculture maintain germplasm collections of edible and wild *Musa* spp. from the Philippines, Southeast Asia and Papua New Guinea (SEA/PNG) that have not been assessed for drought tolerance. Thus, this study was conducted to assess the drought response of 29 *Musa* genotypes from the germplasm collections at seedling stage under greenhouse condition. Drought was imposed on 3 mo-old tissue culture-derived seedlings by withholding water for 2-3 wk, while control plants were watered regularly. Under drought condition, the genotypes differed significantly in terms of plant growth, number of leaf cigars formed, specific leaf area, biomass production and partitioning as well as water use efficiency across water treatment. Only 28% of the banana genotypes allocated more biomass to the roots. Total leaf area production was influenced by significant interaction between water treatment and genotype. Significant genotypic differences in terms of relative leaf folding (RLF) and stomatal conductance were observed, with increased RLF as soil moisture content decreased. Stomatal conductances were significantly affected by the interaction between genotype and time of sampling. The genotypes also differed significantly in their water use efficiency (WUE) with increases ranging 1-70% under drought. WUE was found to be positively correlated with total plant dry weight, root volume, root dry weight and relative leaf folding. Based on the relative performance under drought cultivar, 'Gubao' (BBB) is the most drought tolerant based on total biomass production, root dry weight, root volume and WUE followed by 'P.K. Malaccacina' and 'Tindok'.

Keywords: drought, *Musa* spp., *Musa balbisiana*, stomatal conductance, relative leaf folding, water use efficiency

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine banana industry contributes significantly to the agriculture sector and the economy. Banana ranks 4th among the agricultural crops grown in the Philippines, with total production of 8,884,900 Mt in 2014 and planted area of 442,800 ha (PSA 2015). Banana ranks 2nd to rice in terms of value of production amounting to more than 130 billion pesos in 2014 (PSA 2015). It is consumed largely as snacks, eaten ripe or cooked.

Due to its high rainfall requirement, banana is considered as one of the crops that will be most affected by climate change with its accompanying effects on precipitation, temperature, evaporation, runoff, and soil moisture storage (Calberto et al. 2015). With climate change, the traditional banana-growing areas are predicted to experience higher temperatures, and more frequent and longer drought cycles. Moreover, climate change is predicted to cause shifts in areas suitable for cultivation of a wide range of crops. In banana, 4.25% reduction in crop production area is predicted (Singh 2011). Extending

banana production to drier areas is inevitable to meet increasing food demand, but with subsequent reduction in yields. In East African highland an annual rainfall of <1100 mm could result to 8-28% reduction in bunch weight with maximum bunch weight losses of 1.5-3.1 kg or 8-10% for every 100 mm decline in rainfall (van Asten et al. 2011). In the Philippines, DOST-PAGASA's technical report, 'Climate Change in the Philippines', predicted that by 2020 and 2050 there will be reduction in rainfall in most provinces during the summer season, and reduction in rainfall during the southwest monsoon in Mindanao where most of the commercial banana production is located. In bananas, drought stress has an adverse effect on fruit initiation (Robinson and Alberts 1986) while during flower initiation, drought resulted in reduced number of hands/finger (Holder and Gumbs 1982). Drought stress occurring during the whole growth cycle affects both the number of hands/fingers and fruit-filling period (Goenaga and Irizarry 1995). Drought reduced the leaf and root dry weight by as much as 45% of glasshouse grown banana seedlings

(Mahouachi 2009). Photosynthesis, stomatal conductance and rate of elongation of emerging leaves were also significantly reduced under limiting moisture (Thomas and Turner 1998).

In terms of drought tolerance, a number of researches have given support to the contention that the B genome confers tolerance to drought. Thomas et al. (1998) reported that cultivars Lady Finger (AAB) and Bluggoe (ABB) were less sensitive to leaf-air vapour pressure deficit than variety Williams (AAA). Moreover, *in vitro* assessment of varieties with different genomic constitutions, AAAn, AA, AAB and ABB under mild osmotic stress showed that ABB varieties had the smallest stress-induced growth reduction (Vanhove et al. 2012).

The Philippines have a number of native and wild *Musa* spp. containing the B genome, that are presently maintained by the National Plant Genetic Resources Laboratory (NPGRL) and Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI) alongside with the Southeast Asia *Musa* germplasm. These collections have never been evaluated for drought tolerance. Since the selection and development of drought-tolerant crop varieties is one of the long-term adaptation measures that will lessen the impact of climate change, it is imperative that germplasm accessions at the NPGRL and BPI be evaluated for drought tolerance. Thus, this study aimed to assess the growth and physiological traits of 29 wild and edible *Musa* spp. in response to drought at seedling stage under greenhouse condition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Materials and Experimental Design

Twenty-nine *Musa* spp. consisting of wild (BBw), edible *Musa balbisiana* (BB/BBB), and interspecific hybrids (ABB/AAB/ ABBB) including *Musa acuminata* cv. 'Grand Naine' (AAA) and *M. balbisiana* cv. 'Cardaba' (BBB) as check cultivars were evaluated for their response to drought under greenhouse condition in two sets (Batch 1 and Batch 2) (Table 1). Three month-old tissue culture-derived seedlings were initially potted out and maintained in black plastic bags (3 in x 3 in x 6 in) for 2 mo prior to transplanting into 16-liter capacity black plastic pails containing 10 kg of soil. Transplanting of Batch 1 (17 entries including check cultivars, commenced in March 2011, while Batch 2 (14 entries inclusive of 2 check cultivars) started in June 2011.

The first evaluation was conducted in March 2011, a summer month, while the second batch was planted in June 2011, the start of the rainy season with frequent occurrence of overcast sky during the duration of the experiment (Figure 1). Greenhouse temperature ranged 26-38°C with relative humidity ranging 40-65%. Soil moisture content (SMC) dropped from 46% 1 d after the last watering to 8% at the termination of both Batch 1 and 2 trials.

The soil used was clay loam with 29% and 14% moisture retention at field capacity and permanent

wilting point, respectively. The soil pH, organic matter content and available P (Bray) was 5.6, 3.03% and 64 ppm, respectively. The pails were arranged in a split-plot design with water regimes [well-watered (control) and drought] as the main plots, and banana genotypes as subplots. Drought was imposed 1 mo after transplanting by withholding water from drought-treated plants. Well-watered control pots were regularly irrigated back to field capacity.

Plant Growth Evaluation

Several plant growth parameters were measured during the course of drought imposition. Plant height measurements were recorded from the time of drought imposition until the termination of the experiment. Measurements were taken from the base of the plant to the 'V' point, the meeting point of the two youngest fully opened leaves (Ortiz and Vuylsteke 1998). The number of new leaf cigars formed were monitored every three 3 d during the drought period along with relative leaf folding (RLF).

Relative leaf folding. The RLF of the third youngest fully expanded leaf on drought plants was measured every 3 d after drought imposition until the termination of the trial at 700 hr until 800 hr. Measurements were taken near the center of the lamina margins. RLF was computed following the equation of Turner and Thomas (1998):

$$RLF = 1-w/W$$

where:

W = maximum distance between lamina margins

w = actual distance between lamina margins

Total leaf area. The length of the lamina and the width at the widest part of the leaf lamina were measured and total leaf area was calculated by multiplying lamina length and width with the correction factor 0.83 (Summerville 1944).

Biomass Production and Partitioning. Plant samples collected at the termination of the trial were partitioned into leaves, stems and roots. Roots were washed thoroughly, and together with leaves and stem samples, air-dried for at least 1 wk prior to oven-drying at 60-70°C for 2-3 d. Root shoot ratio was calculated from shoot and root dry weights obtained.

Stomatal conductance. Stomatal conductance was monitored on the third youngest fully expanded leaf from the start until the end of the treatment period using a steady state porometer (Leaf Porometer, Decagon Devices Inc. Pullman WA). Readings were taken from 2 plants per replication for the drought treatment every 2 d during the duration of the treatment.

Root Volume

Washed roots were blotted dry, and the root volume was determined using the water displacement method (Burdett 1979). The roots were placed in plastic graduated cylinders containing known volume of water, and the water displaced with the root

Table 1. *Musa* spp. cultivars evaluated for drought tolerance at seedling stage under greenhouse condition

Cultivar	Genome	Source ¹
Batch 1		
98 363	BBw	PHL
98 364	BBw	PHL
98 580	BBw	PHL
Cardaba	BBB	PHL
Grand Naine	AAA	
Gubao	BBB	PHL
K. Namwa	ABB	SEA/PNG
Latundan	AAB	PHL
Maduranga	ABB	PHL
Matavia	ABB	PHL
Paa Dalaga	ABB	PHL
Pelipia	ABB	PHL
PK Malaccacina	AAB	SEA/PNG
Pokpok	AAB	SEA/PNG
Saba Puti	BBB	PHL
Tindok	ABB	PHL
Tiparot	ABBB	PHL
Batch 2		
98 617	BBw	PHL
98 631	BBw	PHL
99 088	BBw	PHL
Abuhon	BB	PHL
Cardaba	BBB	PHL
Dippig	BBB	PHL
Grand Naine	AAA	
K. Khai Boran	AAB	SEA/PNG
K. Namwa Luang	ABB	SEA/PNG
Kabai	AAB	SEA/PNG
Mundo	BBB	PHL
P. Raja Talong	AAB	SEA/PNG
P. Seribu	AAB	SEA/PNG
Saba Hapon	BBB	PHL

¹PHL-Philippines; SEA/PNG-Southeast Asia/Papua New Guinea

submergence was recorded as the root volume (cm³). The measured roots were air dried then oven-dried at 60-70°C for 2-3 d for root dry weight determination.

Water Use Efficiency (WUE)

WUE was calculated as the ratio of plant dry weight to the total amount of water used (Ehdaie and Waines 1993). Water use of the plants was determined by weighing the pots every 3 d where weight loss was attributed to water use. Drought plants were not rewatered while in control plants, the actual loss in weight was replenished by adding water to obtain the weight of the pail at field capacity. Pots without plants were maintained to account for water loss due to evaporation.

Statistical Analysis

Measurements were subjected to ANOVA using SASTM software (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, North Carolina 2002-2004). Correlation analysis was

Figure 1. Climatic condition at the time of *Musa* spp. evaluation for drought tolerance at seedling stage.

performed to determine the relationship between the traits using the CORR procedure and comparisons between means were made using Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD).

RESULTS

The length of time that the banana plants were subjected to water stress differed for the 2 batches. The evaluation for Batch 1 was terminated 2 wk after drought imposition whereas drought treatment for Batch 2 was terminated after 3 wk. The difference in the duration of drought treatment was attributed to the differences in prevailing environmental condition for each evaluation.

Plant Growth

Plant height. During the evaluation period plant height was significantly reduced by the drought treatment (Table 2). The height reduction in Batch 1

Table 2. Increase in plant height of 29 *Musa* spp. grown under drought and irrigated conditions after drought trial termination

Cultivar	Height Increment, cm plant ⁻¹			
	Control	Drought	Mean ¹	Reduction (%)
Batch 1				
98 363	19.28	5.53	12.41 a-c	71
98 364	21.50	6.22	13.86 a	71
98 580	13.61	5.23	9.42 bc	62
Cardaba	14.95	6.03	10.49 a-c	60
Grand Naine	15.50	4.35	9.93 a-c	72
Gubao	12.11	7.11	9.61 a-c	41
K Namwa	17.71	4.68	11.20 a-c	74
Latundan	12.95	3.85	8.40 c	70
Maduranga	17.67	5.81	11.74 a-c	67
Matavia	19.61	5.78	12.69 a-c	71
Paa Dalaga	13.06	6.07	9.56 a-c	54
Pelipia	17.33	6.33	11.83 a-c	63
PK Malaccacina	16.39	6.13	11.26 a-c	63
Pokpok	15.78	4.05	9.92 a-c	74
Saba Puti	21.83	8.12	14.98 a	63
Tindok	14.11	5.01	9.56 a-c	64
Tiparot	15.67	5.16	10.42 a-c	67
Mean ¹	16.41 a	5.62 b		
Batch 2				
98 617	32.80	7.90	20.35 a	76
98 631	24.73	6.33	15.53 a	74
99 088	31.93	8.60	20.27 a	73
Abuhon	27.53	8.20	17.87 a	70
Cardaba	28.40	7.30	17.85 a	74
Dippig	30.33	8.77	19.55 a	71
Grand Naine	25.27	6.97	16.12 a	72
K. Khai Boran	30.60	9.73	20.17 a	68
K. Namwa Luang	30.13	7.23	18.68 a	76
Kabai	29.47	8.77	19.12 a	70
Mundo	22.97	8.17	15.57 a	64
P Seribu	28.70	7.27	17.98 a	75
P. Raja Talong	24.10	5.47	14.78 a	77
Saba Hapon	29.73	6.27	18 a	79
Mean ¹	28.34 a	7.64 b		

¹Means in a row or column followed by similar letter(s) within batch are not significantly different at 5% level Tukey's HSD

entries ranged 41-74% with the highest reduction shown by 'K. Namwa' and 'Pokpok'. Higher percent reductions of 64-79% in height increment was observed in Batch 2, possibly due to longer exposure to drought. 'Grand Naine' and 'Cardaba', the reference varieties, showed 70% reduction in height for both batches. In terms of frequency distribution of the genotypes tested, 55% had height reductions from 71% while 38% of the genotypes had reduced heights by 60-69%. The remaining 7% of the genotypes showed less than 59% height reduction.

Table 3. Number of leaf cigars formed by 17 *Musa* spp. grown under drought and irrigated conditions during the two weeks drought imposition

Cultivars	Number of leaf Cigars			
	Control	Drought	Mean ¹	Reduction (%)
98 364	2.33	1.89	2.11ab	19
98-363	2.67	1.67	2.17ab	37
98-580	3.22	2.00	2.61a	38
Cardaba	2.44	2.00	2.22ab	18
Grand Naine	2.56	1.67	2.11ab	35
Gubao	2.22	1.67	1.94b	25
K Nanwa	2.45	1.89	2.17ab	23
Latundan	2.67	2.00	2.33ab	25
Maduranga	2.89	2.33	2.61a	19
Matavia	2.44	2.11	2.28ab	14
Paa Dalaga	2.67	1.89	2.28ab	29
Pelipia	2.89	2.00	2.45ab	31
PK Malaccacina	2.56	1.78	2.17ab	31
Pokpok	2.67	1.67	2.17ab	37
Saba Puti	2.78	2.22	2.5ab	20
Tindok	2.55	1.55	2.05ab	39
Tiparot	2.44	1.67	2.06ab	32
Mean ¹	2.61 a	1.88 b		

¹Means in a row or column followed by similar letter(s) are not significantly different at 5% level Tukey's HSD

Number of leaf cigars formed. The average number of leaf cigars formed during stress period was also adversely affected, with an average number of 2 cigars formed under drought while an average of 3 cigars were formed in the control for Batch 1 or equivalent to an average 33% reduction (Table 3). Drought reduced the number of leaf cigars in all the genotypes with the highest reduction observed in 'Tindok' while the lowest reduction was seen in 'Matavia'. On the other hand, there was significant variety by water treatment interaction in Batch 2 wherein most of the genotypes were adversely affected by drought as shown by 31-50% reduction, whereas only 15% reduction was observed in 'Mundo' (Figure 2). Three entries; 98 631, 'K. Khai Boran' and 'Mundo' formed more than 2 leaf cigars during drought while the remaining 90% produced less than 2 leaf cigars. In contrast, all the entries in the well-watered treatment formed more than 2 leaf cigars.

Relative leaf folding. RLF increased with the depletion of soil moisture content. Significant differences among entries were observed from 6 d after last watering up to the termination of the experiment, i.e. 14 d after last watering for Batch 1 (Figure 3). In Batch 2, significant differences among entries were observed from the 15th to the 21st d after last watering. With RLF value of 1.0 corresponding to

Figure 2. Effect of water regime on number of leaf cigars formed among 14 edible and wild *Musa* spp.

fully folded leaf (Turner and Thomas 1998), the range obtained was 0.17-0.60 for Batch 1 and 0.18-0.69 for Batch 2. At the termination of the experiment, maximum RLF values of 0.6 were observed in 'K. Namwa' (Batch 1) and 0.69 in 'P. Raja Talong' (Batch 2). The significant variety and time of sampling interaction observed in terms of relative leaf fold indicated that there were entries which showed erratic leaf folding while some showed continuous increase in RLF with the progression of drought.

Total leaf area. Significant cultivar x water regime interaction was observed in terms of total leaf area (Figure 4). Under well-watered condition, cultivar 'Latundan', an interspecific hybrid had the biggest total leaf area of 5935 cm² plant⁻¹ which was significantly higher than the total leaf area produced by the remaining 15 entries. 'Latundan's total leaf area was comparable with that of hybrid 'Pokpok'. The largest total leaf area under drought was measured from hybrid, 'P.K. Malaccacina' with total leaf area of 2900.94 cm² plant⁻¹. This total leaf area of 'P.K. Malaccacina' was only half the total area produced under well-watered condition by cultivar Lakatan. Thus, under drought 41% of the genotypes produced leaves with total leaf area of 2000-3000 cm² while 47% had total leaf area in the range of 1000-2000 cm². Two entries, 'Tindok' and accession 98-580 even had total leaf area of less than 1000 cm². In contrast, the control plants had total leaf area in the range of 3000-6000 cm².

In Batch 1 the adverse effect of drought was observed among cultivars with percent reduction in leaf area ranging 32-77%. The highest reduction was observed in wild *M. balbisiana* accession 98-580 while the lowest reduction was observed in *M. balbisiana* cultivar 'Gubao'. The reference cultivars, 'Grand Naine' and 'Cardaba' had 62 and 60% reduction in total leaf area, respectively.

Significant water treatment-cultivar interaction was also obtained in Batch 2 which showed that drought reduced total leaf area by 50-76%. Total leaf area

Figure 3. Relative leaf folding of 29 edible and wild *Musa* spp. with drought progression

under well-watered condition varied significantly among entries with hybrid 'K. Khai Boran' having the highest total leaf area of 8085 cm² plant⁻¹.

Specific leaf area which pertains to leaf area per unit leaf dry weight was also adversely affected by limiting moisture as indicated by percent reductions ranging 25.56-62.23%. Reductions of 0.43-17.49% were not deemed significant, thus only 7 cultivars showed significant reductions in specific leaf area in Batch 1. The cultivars that were not significantly affected by drought were 'Tiparot', 'Paa Dalaga' and 'Maduranga' which even exhibited increases in specific leaf area ranging 1.78-3.85% under drought condition. In contrast, the reference cultivars, Cardaba and Grand Naine had reductions of 18 and 36%, respectively. For Batch 2, only the main treatment effects were found significant in terms of specific leaf area (Table 4). The imposition of drought reduced specific leaf area by 8% while the genotypes varied significantly across water treatment.

Biomass production and partitioning. Water stress resulted in total plant dry weight reduction ranging from 45-58% (Table 5). The highest reduction was observed in Batch 2 screening due to longer exposure to drought. Significant genotypic differences in terms of total dry weight were observed in both batches across water treatment. In Batch 1, the highest total

Table 4. Specific leaf area of 14 *Musa* spp. grown under drought and irrigated conditions at three weeks after drought imposition

Cultivar	Specific leaf area			Reduction (%)
	Control	Drought	Mean	
98 617	273.50	286.82	280.16 a	-5
98 631	376.52	362.80	369.66 a	4
99 088	352.84	282.63	317.73 a	20
Abuhon	362.63	320.50	341.56 a	12
Cardaba	353.75	283.32	318.54 a	20
Dippig	323.30	328.35	325.82 a	-2
Grand Naine	325.07	354.97	340.02 a	-9
K Khai Boran	403.01	362.32	382.67 a	10
K Namwaluang	330.30	295.42	312.86 a	11
Kabai	356.44	346.51	351.47 a	3
Mundo	300.38	307.10	303.74 a	-2
P Raja Talong	348.43	252.60	300.52 a	28
P Seribu	321.04	202.38	261.71 a	37
Saba hapon	293.89	341.93	317.91 a	-16
Mean	337.22 a	309.12 b		

¹Means in a row or column followed by similar letter(s) are not significantly different at 5% level Tukey's HSD

dry weight was obtained from 'Pokpok' (AAB), while the lowest was obtained from variety 'Maduranga'. In general, the adverse effect of drought on total dry matter yield was observed among the 29 *Musa* spp. cultivars wherein most of the entries had more than 40% reduction in total dry weight. The check 'Cardaba' proved to be even more adversely affected by drought than 'Grand Naine' and the other *M. balbisiana* varieties as shown by its 55% reduction in dry matter.

Mean root dry weight was significantly reduced by drought with reductions of 49% and 65% in Batches 1 and 2, respectively (Table 6). Moreover, the banana accessions tested also exhibited significant variation in root dry weight across water treatment. In Batch 1, 'K. Namwa' (ABB), 'Pokpok' (AAB) and 'Grand Naine' (AAA) and in Batch 2, 'Saba Hapon' (BBB), 'Dippig' (BBB), and 98-617 (BBw) had the highest mean root dry weights. Root dry weight reductions in Batches 1 and 2 ranged 35-58% and 42-77%, respectively. Among the 29 entries, only 11 banana cultivars had less than 50% root dry weight reduction, of which 2 were of the BBB genome, 2 with ABB, 2 wild accessions (BBw), 4 hybrids AAB, and 1 tetraploid ABBB. Seven entries were from the Philippine collection; 'Saba Puti' (BBB), 'Gubao' (BBB), 'Tindok' (ABB), 'Matavia' (ABB), 98-363 (BBw), and 'Tiparot' (ABBB).

The calculated root-shoot (RS) ratios showed a general reduction of 8 and 3%, for Batches 1 and 2 respectively, while there were significant variation among cultivars across water treatment (Table 7). Relatively, low percent reductions in root-shoot ratio was obtained among the 29 *Musa* cultivars with less than 15% maximum reduction in Batch 1 evaluation

Figure 4. Total leaf area of 29 *Musa* spp. grown in well-watered and drought conditions.

and 29% maximum reduction in Batch 2 (Figure 5). For the 2 batches, 8 cultivars had increased biomass allocated to the roots under drought condition namely; 98-363 (BBw), 99-088 (BBw), 'Maduranga' (ABB), 'Gubao' (BBB), 'Abuhon' (BB), 'Dippig' (BBB), 'Mundo' (BBB), and 'K. Namwa Luang' (ABB).

Stomatal conductance. Stomatal conductances were significantly affected by the interaction between the genotype and the time of sampling. This was observed in the 2 batches of evaluation conducted. Genotypes showed an increase in stomatal conductance on the 4th d after irrigation was withheld (Figure 6), Batch 1, March 2011). This behavior could be brought about by an increase in solar radiation which could have resulted in increased stomatal opening and transpirational loss of water. However, after this period, stomatal conductance declined with decreasing soil moisture; stomatal conductances were already very low on the 8th day after the last irrigation.

Banana cultivars in Batch 2 also showed significantly different stomatal conductances with decreasing soil moisture (Figure 6, Batch 2, June 2011). However, the weather was very inconsistent at this time, with rains interspersed with sunny days. Porometer readings were confined to those days when there was constant sunlight from 1000 and 1400 hr, and only in experimental units that were exposed to sunlight at the time of measurement.

Table 5. Total dry matter yield of 29 *Musa* spp. grown under drought and irrigated conditions after drought trial termination

Cultivar	Total dry weight, g plant ¹			Reduction (%)
	Control	Drought	Mean ¹	
Batch 1				
98 363	75.87	42.47	59.17 b-f	44
98 364	72.90	35.07	53.98 d-f	52
98 580	81.37	47.30	64.33 a-e	42
Cardaba	98.27	46.47	72.37 a-d	53
Grand Naine	96.83	49.43	73.13 a-c	49
Gubao	72.67	47.50	60.08 b-f	35
K Namwa	91.50	52.70	72.10 a-d	42
Latundan	102.83	50.30	76.57 ab	51
Maduranga	63.53	30.73	47.13 f	52
Matavia	73.67	39.60	56.63 c-f	46
Paa Dalaga	81.27	41.87	61.57 b-f	48
Pelipia	97.87	45.67	71.77 a-d	53
PK Malaccacina	89.40	54.63	72.02 a-d	39
Pokpok	101.57	59.73	80.65 a	41
Saba Puti	58.20	33.33	45.77 f	43
Tindok	80.87	53.60	67.23 a-d	34
Tiparot	66.50	40.37	53.43 c-f	39
Mean ¹	82.65 a	45.34 b		
Batch 2				
98 617	118.90	41.33	80.12 ab	65
98 631	88.57	39.27	63.92 ab	56
99 088	104.37	41.23	72.80 ab	60
Abuhon	84.70	40.73	62.72 ab	52
Cardaba	117.40	50.93	84.17 a	57
Dippig	121.20	52.83	87.02 a	56
Grand Naine	106.83	47.23	77.03 ab	56
K. Khai Boran	117.47	30.23	73.85 ab	74
K. Namwa Luang	96.57	45.53	71.05 ab	53
Kabai	100.67	50.10	75.38 ab	50
Mundo	76.20	32.50	54.35 b	57
P Seribu	109.27	47.90	85.20 a	56
P. Raja Talong	111.90	51.30	81.60 ab	54
Saba Hapon	113.00	40.20	76.60 ab	64
Mean ¹	104.79a	43.67b		

¹Means in a row or column followed by similar letter(s) within batch are not significantly different at 5% level Tukey's HSD

Root Volume

Deep and prolific root systems have been associated with enhanced avoidance of terminal drought stress in other crops like chickpea (Serraj et al. 2004) and rice (Kamoshita et al. 2002). However, the drought evaluation conducted showed the general vulnerability of the *Musa* cultivars tested in terms of root volume reductions which ranged 47-84% (Table 8). Only 4 entries showed less than 50% reduction in root volume; 2 were *M. balbisiana* 'Saba' and 'Gubao' from the Philippines, and 2 hybrids, 'Kunambo' and 'P. Kepok Malaccacina' from SE Asia/PNG collection.

Figure 5. Specific leaf area of 17 *Musa* spp. grown in well-watered and drought conditions.

Figure 6. Stomatal conductance of 29 edible and wild *Musa* spp. with drought progression.

Water Use Efficiency (WUE)

All the entries in the 2 greenhouse trials showed increased WUE under drought condition, with an average increase of 44% and 17% for Batches 1 and 2, respectively (Table 9). Moreover, significant genotypic variation was also observed for both batches across water treatment. Two cultivars, 'Mundo' and 'K Khai Boran' showed reductions in WUE under drought while the remaining 27 banana cultivars showed increases ranging 1% to as much as 70%. Cultivars which exhibited more than 50% increase in WUE were 'K Namwa', 'PK Malaccacina', 'Gubao', 'Pokpok' and

Table 6. Root dry weight of 29 *Musa* spp. grown under drought and irrigated conditions after drought trial termination

Cultivar	Root dry weight, g plant ⁻¹			
	Control	Drought	Mean ¹	Reduction (%)
Batch 1				
98 364	18.77	8.30	13.53 c	56
98 363	21.67	12.70	17.18 a-c	41
98 580	24.97	13.10	19.03 a	48
Cardaba	27.37	11.67	19.52 a	57
Grand Naine	27.90	12.37	20.13 a	56
Gubao	21.90	14.27	18.08 a-c	35
K Namwa	26.27	14.37	20.32 a	45
Latundan	27.23	12.03	19.63 ab	56
Maduranga	16.80	8.13	12.47 c	52
Matavia	20.43	10.97	15.70 a-c	46
Paa Dalaga	22.47	10.57	16.52 a-c	53
Pelipia	26.10	10.83	18.47 a-c	58
PK Malaccacina	23.47	12.77	18.12 a-c	46
Pokpok	26.23	14.13	20.18 a	46
Saba Puti	16.40	8.73	12.57 c	47
Tindok	20.80	12.77	16.78 a-c	39
Tiparot	18.97	10.43	14.70 c-e	45
Mean ¹	22.81 a	11.65 b		
Batch 2				
98 617	32.83	11.07	21.95 a	66
98 631	24.27	10.17	17.22 a	58
99 088	25.17	10.57	17.87 a	58
Abuhon	19.43	9.37	14.4 a	52
Cardaba	28.17	11.8	19.98 a	58
Dippig	29.27	14.63	21.95 a	50
Grand Naine	30.23	11.5	20.87 a	62
K. Khai Boran	24.33	5.63	14.98 a	77
K. Namwa Luang	19.73	9.87	14.8 a	50
Kabai	23.33	13.53	18.43 a	42
Mundo	19.33	8.20	13.77 a	58
P Seribu	25.1	10.3	17.7 a	59
P. Raja Talong	25.57	10.47	18.02 a	59
Saba Hapon	36.47	10.33	23.4 a	72
Mean ¹	25.95 a	10.53 b		

¹Means in a row or column followed by similar letter(s) within batch are not significantly different at 5% level Tukey's HSD

Table 7. Root-shoot ratio of 29 *Musa* spp. grown under drought and irrigated conditions after drought trial termination

Cultivar	Root shoot ratio			
	Control	Drought	Mean ¹	Reduction (%)
Batch 1				
98 363	0.3994	0.4260	0.4127 ab	-7
98 364	0.3470	0.3095	0.3282 c	11
98 580	0.4416	0.3832	0.4124 ab	13
Cardaba	0.3824	0.3399	0.3611 bc	11
Grand Naine	0.4008	0.3323	0.3666 a-c	17
Gubao	0.4337	0.4367	0.4352 a	-1
K Namwa	0.4036	0.3731	0.3884 a-c	8
Latundan	0.3611	0.3194	0.3403 c	12
Maduranga	0.3590	0.3663	0.3627 bc	-2
Matavia	0.3814	0.3802	0.3808 a-c	0
Paa Dalaga	0.3813	0.3428	0.3621 bc	10
Pelipia	0.3605	0.3121	0.3363 c	13
PK Malaccacina	0.3561	0.3062	0.3312 c	14
Pokpok	0.3482	0.309	0.3286 c	11
Saba Puti	0.3855	0.3568	0.3711 a-c	7
Tindok	0.3457	0.3120	0.3288 c	10
Tiparot	0.3985	0.3596	0.3790 a-c	10
Mean ¹	0.3815 a	0.3509 b		
Batch 2				
98 617	0.3801	0.3681	0.3741 ab	3
98 631	0.3770	0.3484	0.3627 ab	8
99 088	0.3126	0.3411	0.3269 ab	-9
Abuhon	0.2950	0.2992	0.2971 ab	-1
Cardaba	0.3202	0.3186	0.3194 ab	1
Dippig	0.3196	0.3838	0.3517 ab	-20
Grand Naine	0.3944	0.3241	0.3593 ab	18
K. Khai Boran	0.2611	0.2288	0.2449 b	12
K. Namwa Luang	0.2628	0.2746	0.2687 b	-4
Kabai	0.2972	0.3661	0.3317 ab	-23
Mundo	0.3325	0.3692	0.3509 ab	-11
P Seribu	0.2942	0.2737	0.2839 ab	7
P. Raja Talong	0.2951	0.2564	0.2757 ab	13
Saba Hapon	0.4908	0.3474	0.4191 a	29
Mean ¹	0.3309 a	0.3214 a		

¹Means in a row or column followed by similar letter(s) within batch are not significantly different at 5% level Tukey's HSD

'Tindok'. Interestingly, 'Grand Naine' had higher increase in WUE than 'Cardaba'. Of the top 10 entries in the combined set, 8 were interspecific hybrids from the Philippines and Southeast Asia/Papua New Guinea collections. WUE correlated positively with total plant dry weight, root length, root volume, root dry weight, leaf weight and relative leaf folding.

DISCUSSION

Our results showed the general sensitivity of banana to limiting soil moisture even at seedling stage which support the observation that banana requires a high

amount of moisture to maintain productivity. All the genotypes evaluated regardless of genome constitution exhibited significant reduction in plant height under drought. This sensitivity was further observed in terms of leaf cigar formation which has been previously reported to be due to sensitivity of elongation rate of leaves emerging from the pseudostem of potted banana plants (Thomas and Turner 1998; Hoffman and Turner 1993). The rate of extension of the youngest leaf was thought to be the most sensitive indicator of plant water status (Kallarackal et al. 1990). However, the significant interaction observed in the first batch of screened materials showed that cultivar

Table 8. Root volume of 29 *Musa* spp. grown under drought and irrigated conditions after drought trial termination

Cultivar	Root volume cm ³ plant ⁻¹			
	Control	Drought	Mean ¹	Reduction (%)
Batch 1				
98 364	76.11	26.66	51.39 d	65
98-363	86.11	38.33	62.22 b-d	55
98-580	106.11	45.00	75.56 a-d	58
Cardaba	126.11	44.44	85.28 ab	65
Grand Naine	100.22	43.89	72.06 a-d	56
Gubao	94.44	49.56	72.00 a-d	48
K Namwa	109.45	47.78	78.61 a-c	56
Latundan	112.22	45.00	78.61 a-c	60
Maduranga	85.00	29.44	57.22 a-d	65
Matavia	90.56	45.00	67.78 a-d	50
Paa Dalaga	96.11	39.44	67.78 a-d	59
Pelipia	108.33	42.22	75.28 a-d	61
PK Malaccacina	99.44	50.56	75.00 a-d	49
Pokpok	123.89	56.67	90.28 a	54
Saba Puti	72.78	38.33	55.56 cd	47
Tindok	112.22	46.11	79.17 a-c	59
Tiparot	85.56	37.22	65.00 b-d	56
Mean ¹	99.10a	42.69b		
Batch 2				
98 617	120.53	35.03	77.78 a	71
98 631	131.10	32.77	81.93 a	75
99 088	100.00	28.87	64.43 a	71
Abuhon	80.53	32.23	56.38 a	60
Cardaba	122.23	42.23	82.23 a	65
Dippig	102.23	50.53	76.38 a	51
Grand Naine	111.67	43.90	77.78 a	61
K. Khai Boran	140.00	22.80	81.40 a	84
K. Namwa Luang	83.87	40.57	62.22 a	52
Kabai	77.77	37.23	57.50 a	52
Mundo	97.23	30.57	63.90 a	69
P Seribu	124.97	38.90	81.93 a	69
P. Raja Talong	127.77	33.33	80.55 a	74
Saba Hapon	112.23	38.90	75.57 a	65
Mean ¹	109.44a	36.28b		

¹Means in a row or column followed by similar letter(s) within batch are not significantly different at 5% level Tukey's HSD

Mundo's production of new leaf was not significantly affected by drought as indicated by 15% reduction in number of leaf cigars formed whereas the remaining genotypes exhibited more than 30% reduction.

Biomass production data showed the general sensitivity of banana to drought with high reduction observed among the genotypes, despite the inherent differences among cultivars observed across water treatment. The adverse effect of drought on biomass production has been reported for economically important crops like barley (Jamieson et al. 1995), rice (Boonjung and Fukai 1996), peanut (Pimratch et al. 2008) and corn (Otegui et al. 1995). On the other hand, increase in root-shoot ratios was observed in most of the cultivars.

Table 9. Water use efficiency of 29 *Musa* spp. grown under drought and irrigated conditions after drought trial termination

Cultivar	Water Use Efficiency, g kg ⁻¹ water used			
	Control	Drought	Mean ¹	Increase (%)
Batch 1				
98 363	3.97	5.45	4.71 a-e	37
98 364	3.57	4.59	4.08 c-e	29
98 580	3.95	5.87	4.91 a-e	49
Cardaba	5.01	6.01	5.51 a-d	20
Grand Naine	4.54	6.58	5.56 a-e	45
Gubao	3.86	6.37	5.12 a-e	65
K Namwa	4.08	6.93	5.50 a-e	70
Latundan	4.66	6.75	5.71 a-c	45
Maduranga	3.5	3.84	3.67 e	10
Matavia	3.71	5.23	4.47 b-e	41
Paa Dalaga	4.48	6.2	5.34 a-e	38
Pelipia	4.26	6.28	5.27 a-e	47
PK Malaccacina	4.5	7.45	5.98 ab	66
Pokpok	4.85	7.97	6.41 a	64
Saba Puti	3.31	4.38	3.84 de	32
Tindok	4.41	6.87	5.64 a-d	56
Tiparot	3.99	5.10	4.54 b-e	28
Mean ¹	4.16a	5.99b		
Batch 2				
98 617	4.87	4.94	4.91 ab	1
98 631	4.41	4.90	4.65 ab	11
99 088	4.47	5.22	4.85 ab	17
Abuhon	4.24	5.00	4.62 ab	18
Cardaba	5.03	6.04	5.54 ab	20
Dippig	4.92	6.28	5.60 ab	28
Grand Naine	4.95	6.08	5.52 ab	23
K. Khai Boran	4.54	3.85	4.19 b	-15
K. Namwa Luang	4.41	5.61	5.01 ab	27
Kabai	4.59	6.26	5.43 ab	36
Mundo	4.59	4.27	4.43 ab	-7
P Seribu	4.50	5.82	5.16 ab	29
P. Raja Talong	4.79	6.56	5.68 a	37
Saba Hapon	4.77	5.17	4.97 ab	8
Mean ¹	4.65b	5.43a		

¹Means in a row or column followed by similar letter(s) within batch are not significantly different at 5% level Tukey's HSD

Increased biomass allocation to the roots to source water is known to be a major plant response to diminishing moisture to reduce water consumption and increase water absorption (Erice et al. 2010; Blum 1996).

The significant genotypic differences under drought observed in Batch 1, in terms of total leaf area production indicate the differences in coping mechanism of the cultivars to survive the stress. Genotypic variation in total leaf area production were also observed in cowpea (Anyia and Herzog 2004). The plasticity in leaf area under drought condition has been reported to be the mode by which drought-stressed crops regulates water use (Blum 1996).

The closing of the stomates has been reported to be the earliest plant response to moisture stress (Schroeder et al. 2001) while a network of signaling pathways has been reported to regulate stomatal movement (Nemhauser et al. 2006). With the drop in soil water status, a signal exchange between the roots and leaves causes reduction in stomatal opening, resulting to reduced stomatal conductance. The role of plant hormones abscisic acid (ABA), jasmonic acid, brassinosteroids, cytokinins and ethylene in the regulation of stomatal opening has been reviewed by Daszkowska-Golec and Szareko (2013). In the case of banana, stomatal closure occur as soil starts to dry (Turner et al. 2007). Genotypic differences in stomatal sensitivity among banana cultivars was reported by Ekayanake et al. (1994) and was used as basis in the identification of tolerant and intolerant banana cultivars.

This study showed that banana have enhanced water use efficiency under drought condition similar to reported studies in other crops wherein WUE increased under water limiting conditions (Craufurd et al. 1999; Ismail et al. 1994; Li et al. 2000; Peuke et al. 2006). Ploidy number also affects WUE. In wheat, diploid and hexaploid wheat have significantly higher water use efficiency, compared to tetraploid wheat (Khazaei et al. 2010). In this study, the triploids K. Namwa (ABB), P.K. Malaccacina (AAB), Gubao (BBB), Pokpok (AAB) and Tindok (ABB) were among the top 5 genotypes in terms of WUE while only 1 diploid, 98 580 (BBw) was in the top 10 list. Tiparot (ABBB) ranked 18th in WUE.

The significant genotypic differences observed across water treatment indicate the inherent variation among Philippine and Southeast Asia/Papua New Guinea collections. Although high reductions in plant height increment, biomass production and root volume were observed, the two trials identified *Musa* cultivars with increased biomass allocation to the roots and high WUE. High biomass allocation to the roots is one desirable characteristic for crops to flourish under moisture limiting condition. Entries with relatively lower reductions in the parameters measured were entries containing the B genome. The top 17 entries all contained the B genome whereas Grand Naine (AAA) ranked 18th. A number of publications have reported that the B genome might be correlated to higher drought tolerance (Ravi et al. 2013; Thomas et al. 1998).

CONCLUSION

Twenty-nine wild and edible *Musa* spp. from the Philippine and Southeast Asia/Papua New Guinea collections showed high sensitivity to drought stress. The vulnerability of the germplasm evaluated to drought was shown by the reduction in plant growth parameters evaluated such as plant height, leaf cigar formation, relative leaf folding, biomass production, stomatal conductance and total leaf area. Root volume was also adversely affected by drought. Ninety

-three percent of the genotypes evaluated showed enhanced water use efficiency under drought condition.

Ranking of the genotypes based on their relative performance under drought showed that cultivar, 'Gubao' (BBB) ranked first based on average performance in terms of total biomass production, root dry weight, root volume and WUE followed by 'P.K. Malaccacina' and 'Tindok'.

Since the study was conducted only at seedling stage, it is recommended that more long-term studies should be done to test whether the high increase in WUE at seedling stage will translate to high yield under drought condition.

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